

Synthesis and Reactions of Some New Cyano Aroylanils*

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A few α -cyano aroyl anils have been synthesized from some acetophenones and *p*-amino dimethyl aniline, and characterized through the formation of phenylhydrazones, 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, semicarbazones and oximes.

A number of new anils derived from phenyl glyoxal hydrate and a variety of aromatic amino compounds were reported by Malik, Gupta and Taploo^{1,2}. The oximes of many of these anils produced yellow, greenish yellow and green colouration with metal ions and could be employed as analytical reagents.³ They also observed that acetic solutions of anils derived from phenyl glyoxal and *p*-bromo phenyl glyoxal hydrates and *p*-amino dimethyl aniline cause a sharp colour change on reacting with Lewis acids⁴. This change may be attributed to bathochromism and chelation. The probable mechanism for the chelation has been suggested as follows :

Practically very little work seems to have been done on anils (I) in which the hydrogen atom of the azomethine grouping is substituted by a nitrile group. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesize some α -cyano aroyl anils from acetophenones and *p*-amino dimethyl aniline and examine the influence of a nitrile group on bathochromism and chelation. The present communication deals with the synthesis and characteristics of α -cyano aroyl anils derived from acetophenone; *o*-hydroxy, carboxylic acetophenones; *p*-methyl, methoxy, hydroxy, chloro, bromo acetophenones; and *m*-nitro, amino acetophenones.

*Presented at the 5th Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society, Roorkee, 1967.

1. W. U. Malik, D. R. Gupta and C. L. Taploo, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1966, **11**, 210.
2. W. U. Malik, D. R. Gupta and C. L. Taploo, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 525.
3. W. U. Malik, D. R. Gupta and C. L. Taploo, *Indian J. Chem.*, (Communicated).
4. C. L. Taploo, Ph.D. thesis, University of Roorkee, 1967.

α -cyano aroyl anils were synthesized indirectly by reacting sodium cyanide with nitrones⁵ obtained on condensing pyridinium iodides of the corresponding ketones with *p*-nitroso dimethyl aniline. The anils listed in Table-I, were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of corresponding ketones pyridine and iodine for about an hour and the reaction mixture was allowed to cool and acetone was then added. The corresponding pyridinium iodides thus obtained were dissolved in 50% alcohol at 20° and treated with *p*-nitroso dimethyl aniline. To the reaction mixture was added a solution of 10% sodium cyanide and the products were kept in a freezing mixture. The solids thus obtained were filtered and crystallised from ethanol. These anils are soluble in methanol, benzene, toluene and practically insoluble in water.

TABLE I

Aroyl cyanioe anils derived from different acetophenones and p-Amino dimethyl aniline

Sl. No.	Name of the α -cyano compound	Colour	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	% N	
						Calculated	Found
1.	α -Cyano Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₃	145	95.32	15.16	14.98
2.	α -Cyano- <i>p</i> -hydroxy Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	150	87.15	14.33	14.15
3.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -methyl Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₃	170	74.00	14.43	14.28
4.	α -Cyano <i>o</i> -hydroxy Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	166	82.42	14.33	14.06
5.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -methoxy Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	160	91.50	13.68	13.27
6.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -chloro Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₃ Cl	182	65.64	13.48	13.19
7.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -bromo Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₃ Br	175	84.87	11.83	11.57
8.	α -Cyano <i>o</i> -carboxylic Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Green	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃	190	49.00	13.08	12.84
9.	α -Cyano <i>m</i> -nitro Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄	185	43.68	17.39	17.10
10.	α -Cyano <i>m</i> -amino Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₄	218	39.84	19.17	18.77

Phenyhydrazones, 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, semicarbazones and oximes of the anils were prepared by the usual methods. They were obtained almost in theoretical yields and crystallised from ethanol. The characteristics of these derivatives are recorded in Table II.

The oximes of many of these anils produce different colours with metal ions and offer a possibility for being used as analytical reagents.

TABLE II

Characteristics of the derivatives of the Aroyl Cyanioe Anils

Sl. No.	Name of the α -cyano compound	Phenylhydrazones		2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazones		Semi carbazones		Oximes	
		M.P. °C.	% N. Calcd. Found	M.P. °C.	% N. Calcd. Found	M.P. °C.	% N. Calcd. Found	M.P. °C.	% N. Found
1.	α -Cyano Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	120	19.07 18.96	115	21.44 21.39	155	25.14 25.32	166	19.17 19.23
2.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -hydroxy Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil.	160	18.27 18.14	120	20.71 20.67	170	24.00 23.88	178	18.18 18.12
3.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -methyl Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	105	18.37 18.45	126	20.80 20.69	177	24.13 24.45	185	18.30 18.02
4.	α -Cyano <i>o</i> -hydroxy Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	125	18.27 17.96	117	20.71 20.43	182	24.00 23.87	144	18.18 17.96
5.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -methoxy Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	138	17.63 17.48	130	20.12 19.76	180	23.07 22.85	175	17.39 17.25
6.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -chloro Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	108	17.43 17.35	173	19.93 19.50	165	22.79 22.41	102	17.15 16.84
7.	α -Cyano <i>p</i> -bromo Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	124	15.73 15.43	160	18.31 17.92	158	20.38 20.16	129	15.13 14.90
8.	α -Cyano <i>o</i> -carboxylic Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	138	17.03 16.82	192	19.56 19.25	185	22.22 21.88	135	16.66 16.25
9.	α -Cyano <i>m</i> -nitro Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	146	20.38 21.10	115	22.31 21.98	165	25.85 25.53	195	20.77 20.48
10.	α -Cyano <i>m</i> -amino Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	188	21.98 21.63	205	23.72 23.65	198	28.08 27.91	215	22.80 22.47

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. G. Gollakota, Director, S.B.S. & H. U.P. Agricultural University, Pantnagar for providing necessary facilities and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (Y.S.)